

absorbance values at 405 nm in ELISA (Table 2). ASD7 and ASD8 tended to have high RTBV and RTSV

absorbance. Utri Merah and Utri Rajapan had low absorbance. The results indicate a possible correlation

between symptom severity and the level of virus antigens in the plant tissues.

Reaction of IR varieties to tungro (RTV) under various disease pressure

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We conducted field trials to evaluate the reaction of IR varieties to RTV at IIRRI and Guimba (Nueva Ecija, Philippines) in 1984 wet season. One 3-wk-old seedling was transplanted per hill and left for natural infection. Disease symptoms were recorded 1 mo after transplanting, and random leaf samples were tested by latex agglutination for the presence of RTV-associated viruses.

Varietal reaction differed with local disease pressure, as determined by RTV infection of the susceptible check. At IIRRI, with low disease pressure, susceptible check IR22 had only 47% infection; IR36 and IR42, which are moderately resistant to green leafhopper (GLH), had 6 and 15% infection. Varieties with high GLH resistance had lowest RTV infection (see figure). Serological tests showed that IR22 generally was infected with both rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV), as were IR42 and IR36 at lower levels. The other varieties either were not infected or had only a low level of RTSV (see table).

At Guimba, IR62 as well as IR22, IR36, and IR42 had high RTV infection (see figure). RTV-associated viruses occurred in the same pattern as at IIRRI (see table).

RTV infection of IR varieties under different disease pressures. IIRRI and Guimba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1984 wet season.

^a Data from IIRRI Entomology Department.

^b Greenhouse mass screening results, IIRRI Plant Pathology Department: 0-30% infection, resistant (R); 31-60%, intermediate (I); 61-100%, susceptible (S).

Incidence of RTV-associated viruses in naturally infected IR cultivars as detected by latex agglutination. ^a

Variety	Plants infected (%)							
	IIRRI ^b				Guimba			
	RTBV + RTSV	RTBV	RTSV	Healthy	RTBV + RTSV	RTBV	RTSV	Healthy
IR22	52	22	17	8	60	8	21	11
IR36	6	9	26	58	19	11	36	34
IR42	32	13	33	22	34	5	37	24
IR50	0	1	0	99	0	0	2	98
IR52	0	0	0	100	0	1	2	97
IR56	—	—	—	—	3	1	24	72
IR58	5	1	11	83	0	0	3	97
IR60	0	0	0	100	0	1	1	98
IR62	0	0	11	89	10	4	37	48

^a RTBV = rice tungro bacilliform virus, RTSV = rice tungro spherical virus. ^b — = not tested.

The results show that varieties with high insect resistance can escape field

infection better than those with low or moderate resistance.

Reactions of eight rices to tungro (RTV)

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Eight rice varieties were inoculated for 8 h in cages by the mass screening method

or in test tubes with 1, 3, or 5 green leafhoppers (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* per seedling. Seedling infection increased with GLH number. Regardless of GLH number, percentage infection was higher in test tube than in mass inoculation (Table 1).

ARC1 1554 was resistant regardless of

insect number or inoculation method. Basmati 375A reaction changed from resistant to intermediate in the test tube when GLH number increased from 1 to 3 or 5, but was resistant at 5 GLH/ seedling in the mass-inoculation test. IR28 and Ptb 18 reactions changed from resistant to intermediate in the